

Discussion on the Origin of Happiness Below Philosophical and Theological Perspective

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ABSTRACT: Before going into this topic, we must clarify the concept of "Happiness" from the perspective of "Philosophers". as well as the term "Happiness" of "Theologians". If "Philosophy" studies happiness from the perspective of human reason and that reason proves that happiness is the satisfaction of human's internal "material and spiritual" needs in a direct or indirect way (the current understanding is that this perception is proven from scientific theory). Or we can understand Philosophy as the truth of reason. Then "Theology" of happiness belongs to the belief of man about God revealing the world (God's revelation to man is to create needs for man and give man to satisfy those needs), Theology is the truth of faith. However, that faith is not only expressed in words but must be lived out in real life of man. And that happiness lies nowhere else but in the truth of truth. Man's happiness is **the truth that reigns** in the relationship between man and God and between man and man. Jesus said:

"The truth will set you free" [John 8:32].

That is true liberation, that is true liberation. Truth is truth.

KEYWORDS: General theory of happiness; the view of happiness in the Philosophy of "reason"; the view of happiness in the Theology of "faith".

General theory of happiness. So what is happiness? And why do humans not only in the present stage but throughout the history of human existence and development always crave to find it? Some people say that they live most of their lives without finding happiness; many people say that happiness exists in your daily life but you don't realize it?; some people are happy with others but not with themselves; some people think that happiness is material wealth, some people think that happiness is longevity, and many people think that happiness only exists when people have enough abundance in both material and spiritual life; some people are happy when they are with God every day...

So, what is happiness? And what is true happiness? Why do people want to find the nature of happiness and why is human perception of happiness a concern for millennia of theologians and philosophers? Here the author discusses human happiness from two perspectives of reason and faith. The concept of happiness from ancient times to the present must have been defined differently by many scientists. Because they have different perspectives, positions, and beliefs. Even each person can define their own concept of happiness. However, the term happiness can be generalized according to the concept of ordinary human life as used to refer to a human emotional state when a certain need is satisfied in terms of material, spiritual, and faith. So what is the concept of happiness in Philosophy and Theology?

According to theologians, happiness is faith. Faith here is believing in the revelation from God and that happiness is a gift that God promises to bestow and bless upon humans. By practicing faith, we know that God is the source and true happiness of human life: "Blessed is he who trusts in the Lord as his refuge" [Jer 17:7]. Humans are loved by God, protected and blessed by Him on their journey as humans. Therefore, only when they are united with God can humans have complete happiness. The Psalm says: "Taste and see that the Lord is good; blessed is the man who takes refuge in him" [Ps 33:9].

Philosophers consider the objects that affect human happiness to be material and spiritual, also expressed from reality. That means happiness is the satisfaction of material and spiritual needs, and happiness is also making others happy. From there, the concept of happiness is different.

Happiness in "rational" Philosophy. First of all, happiness only exists in humans; so if happiness is the satisfaction of human needs, what are those needs.

Happiness in "Rational" Philosophy is to satisfy both material and spiritual needs of people. First of all, in the world, the existence of matter is objective, universal and diverse. All matter is always moving and changing and each specific matter has certain characteristics and properties. However, in human life, there is always a need for material to survive. Therefore, the satisfaction of

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material needs is always closely linked to human existence. Material that directly serves people sometimes has limits and human needs are limited. Therefore, the satisfaction of material needs is closely linked to happiness. For example, the satisfaction of material needs: when he is hungry, someone else gives him a loaf of bread, he eats it until his stomach is full and his body is very satisfied, that is happiness. And conversely, he cannot be happy when he has nothing in his stomach, that means not satisfying his needs and of course he is not happy. Besides, in human life there is always the presence of spirit. Spirit also appears with humans, it is closely associated with the existence and development of human society through each certain historical period. Therefore, happiness must also be associated with spiritual satisfaction. For example: When we listen to a love song or watch a play that makes our soul, spirit relaxed, love life or happy, that is happiness.

Happiness only exists in humans, philosophers believe that: the concept of happiness represents the level of human thinking, it is a high-level emotion, only in humans, it has a deep humanity and is often influenced by reason. One point to note, happiness is expressed in each specific individual. Because each person has a different way of satisfying needs, even in space and time it also manifests differently.

According to C.Marx and F.Engels, man is the highest product of nature. He believes that: "nature (...) is the inorganic body of man" [8. p.135], the result of material evolution, "the most complex body that nature can produce" [9. p.475]. In this sense, man is first of all a part of nature. Therefore, man has full biological nature and species nature. On the other hand, man is not passive before nature, but on the contrary, "man also affects nature, transforms nature and creates new conditions for his own survival" [9.p.720]. Man's impact on nature increases gradually according to his own needs and awareness of his living and existing conditions. And happiness also appears with the needs in human existence. Therefore, happiness is a psychological state when we feel satisfied with a certain need in the material or spiritual field.

However, happiness is not simply a feeling of personal satisfaction but also the ability to bring happiness to others. Heraclitus once said "If material satisfaction is happiness, then we can consider the cow to be happy...". Therefore, happiness is not simply a matter of material satisfaction, but also of making others satisfied. Karl Marx said "The happiest man is the one who brings happiness to the greatest number of people..."; "Only beasts turn away from the pain of their fellow men, and care for their own happiness".

Here, according to the philosopher Karl Marx's view of happiness, it is comprehensive, reflecting the true meaning of happiness. Because, if we say that happiness is only material or spiritual satisfaction, it is correct but not enough, it will include happiness on the pain of others. For example: a hungry person, he takes away someone else's loaf of bread, he eats his fill and satisfies his hunger, then he will be happy. However, the person who loses the loaf of bread means being hungry and deprived of happiness. Thus, happiness on the unhappiness of others. According to Karl Marx, one's happiness must be linked to the happiness of others. About the idea of happiness of Karl Marx is somewhat consistent with the advice of the ancient Vietnamese: "What you do not want, do not do to others; What you want to do, do to others." That is happiness.

So what is the fundamental cause of human unhappiness? According to the author, the fundamental cause is the falsehood that appears in the relationship between people, taking away happiness. To discuss my point of view, I invite you to go with me back to human history. In the primitive social stage, people lived together, ate together, slept together... All wealth was shared. They lived together very happily, that society still had power, but it was a serving power. The appearance of material appropriation caused a crack in that common happiness, and falsehood also appeared from here. It was the appearance of falsehood that caused the relationship between people to crack and break. The state appeared with the role of mending those broken pieces. Throughout the historical process, up to now, there have been many forms of state, but up to now, that relationship has not been completely resolved. Even today, lies are still common, so common that human error is sometimes considered a culture. Look at the works that have been awarded, recognized for excellence in novels, poetry and other genres of writing. Do those works reflect the truth? If the content is not true, depicting things that do not exist in real life, then it is false and vice versa.

How to Win Friends and Influence People is a self-help book , the best-selling book of all time. This book was written by Dale Carnegie and was first published in 1936, it has sold 15 million copies worldwide. It was also a New York Times bestseller for 10 years. The work is considered the first and best book of its kind, having a life-changing influence on millions of people around the world. However, the basic content of the book is **to win people's hearts**, and to win people's hearts means we have to flatter others. And flattery is false, not the truth.

The author further discusses the issue of truth in human-human relationships to see the position and role of truth today. First of all , why is there war? Everyone is aware that war is bloodshed, and as humans, no one wants to shed blood. So why does blood still flow in war? It is because people are living without respecting the truth or living falsely. Our ancestors have lived on this land for generations, I also have a family with children who are living happily. You were also born on another land, also connected to your ancestors and you also have a family with happy children like me. We have not done you any harm, so why did you invade my country, exploit my people and destroy my family, causing us to disperse. There are many reasons for the answer, but in general, you have lived falsely, you are living falsely (looting is false). So if people live honestly with each other, there will certainly be no war.

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The author examines the truth in the relationship between people in a particular nation. Why are there rich and poor people? Why do some people despise one and respect another? Some people argue that the reason there are rich and poor people is because people have differences in intelligence and health. Therefore, people are different in terms of possession of wealth. This explanation sounds very reasonable and I agree to some extent. However, it does not convince me completely, because those people live without the truth **in loving each other**. If people live truthfully, they will love and share with each other, then private property will have no place among us.

Thus, to have complete happiness, we must **eliminate falsehood**. If humanity eliminates falsehood, it means that courts will have no work, laws will not be needed... Then the state will inevitably perish. How wonderful the world would be if there were no war, no army, no weapons of destruction... If people only focused on material production, spiritual production and human production, then humanity would be completely happy.

Happiness from the perspective of theologians. Scholars note that the author of this article does not intend to confuse the concept of happiness with truth, but the author considers the logic in the relationship between happiness and truth in the general concept of theologians. That means happiness is associated with truth. However, to have the truth about happiness, people must live in truth. Thereby, truth is the most comprehensive and also the source of happiness.

When discussing the origin of happiness, theologians identify **happiness as Truth**, and the truth here means truth. **So happiness is truth. So what is truth?** According to theologians, truth is not only **used to** refer to knowledge whose content is consistent with objective reality; that consistency has been tested and proven by practice, but also used to refer to faith in the words of God. Therefore, when talking about happiness from the theologian's point of view, we understand happiness very simply as **living in the truth, respecting the truth, loving the truth that God has taught**. If we can do that truth, then people will not only be happy in the reality on earth but also happy in heaven (when people die). Thus, that happiness is universal to people both in the present and after death.

So where does the truth come from? In the Creation Theory, right from the beginning of the universe and of course with humans, God not only wanted humans to live happily, but also wanted humans to enjoy eternal happiness. In Genesis 2:7, Adam carries the idea of the first man, the one created by God and belongs to the most noble children of God. In the Bible, Adam is also mentioned as God's masterpiece: God molded Adam from clay and breathed life into him in the final chapter of the Creation Theory. In the first chapter of Genesis, God's "promise and blessing" to Adam and Eve. God's promise is to give Adam and Eve **the freedom to choose**. If they obey God, they will have a happy life forever, otherwise they will die.

God promised to confirm Adam in a state of eternal life and happiness from Him, described in the Bible as follows: "And I heard a loud voice from heaven saying, 'Behold, the tabernacle of God is with men, and He will dwell with them; and they shall be His people, and God Himself will be with them, and will be their God. And God will wipe away every tear from their eyes; and there shall be no more death, neither shall there be sorrow, nor crying, neither shall there be any more pain, for the former things have passed away.'" [Revelation 21:3-4]. In response, God made demands on Adam to love, trust, and obey God. This included specifically not eating from the tree of the knowledge of good and evil. He attached a death curse to breaking His word [Genesis 1:26-28; 2:15-17].

Through the above "promises and blessings", we can see that God certainly does not want people to disobey Him, which means that God always wants people to live happily. This is also clearly shown in the creation of Eve by God when Adam was sleeping, God took one of his ribs to create his wife, Eve. Adam and Eve became the first family. God created the first two people to share the "happiness" in the Garden of Eden. **So how did Adam feel?** And the answer is that he was so happy that he exclaimed: "See who the Lord has made from my rib! Here, someone like me!" That is happiness. And **why did God take a rib?** Instead of a leg or shoulder bone to create a solid Eve? The answer to this question must be linked to happiness. That was probably God's intention to show equality between two people, if we take the shoulder bone, the woman will be on top of the man, if we take the leg bone, the man will trample on the woman. So, the equality that God arranged for humans right from the first moment of creating Adam and Eve so that the two people would be equal, in harmony, creating happiness for them. And that was also the origin of happiness for the first human.

However, it was not as God expected when Adam and Eve committed the sin of disobedience by "eating the forbidden fruit", death appeared. Through that, happiness lost its original nature, or in other words, the eternal happiness that God gave to humans was cracked, God took back the happiness of eternal life. From the crack between humans and God, an imperfection and became a destiny that humans had to accept. That crack is also understood through the snake saying to the woman: "You will not surely die! For God knows that when you eat that fruit, your eyes will be opened and you will be like God, knowing good and evil". The woman saw that the fruit of the tree looked delicious and beautiful, so she believed it and picked it, ate it, and gave it to her husband to eat... God asked the woman. The woman said: "The snake deceived me and I ate it". Thus, falsehood appeared, which means the truth was violated.

So after committing sin, did you lose all happiness? .. with love, God gives people new happiness. However, that happiness is not as complete as before, but this new happiness is intertwined between physical pain and joy in the life revealed by God. And God

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promises to give those who live according to His "truth" to eternal happiness, this happiness must go through the painful struggle between the body and the soul before people die (according to Augustine's argument).

To find the original happiness of the "first man". God sent his only son, Jesus, to become a human being and establish the blood covenant of Jesus, the Son of God who became a human being [Mt 26,26-29]. So who is Jesus?. Most scholars agree that Jesus was a Jew from Galilee, born around the beginning of the first century and died between 30 and 36 AD in Judea, he only lived and worked in Galilee and Judea and not elsewhere [11-12. pp. 42-303]. The Gospels only focus on the last three years of Jesus' life on earth, especially the last week before being crucified to redeem humanity. And in this last week He made a covenant with humanity. This is the covenant considered by mankind as the Charter of the Kingdom of Heaven.

What is Jesus's principle? And what is Jesus's thought? When talking about Jesus's thought in general and his thought of happiness in particular, the author does not see much. Because he lived for 33 years, there was not much time to help him express all his thoughts to people. Moreover, due to socio-political issues and writing barriers, Jesus' new thoughts were also restrained to a certain extent. However, with such a small number, the question arises: with those simple sermons, why did they have such a great impact on humanity? For theologians, without hesitation, the answer is that he went right and went straight to the expectations of humanity, **which is the thirst for truth**. It sounds very simple, but analyzing "truth" it is the cause of all causes. Or in other words, Jesus's thoughts reflect the core of truth.

The author wants to discuss the truth of **Jesus**. This issue has many opinions from history to the present that are still being debated. However, the author asserts his own subjective opinion that: nothing else but Jesus came to earth to find back some of the happiness that was lost from the beginning. That is, the principle of finding **back the truth "truth"**. **Because only the truth can bring true happiness.**

When speaking about the truth in Jesus, when being interrogated at the palace of Governor Pilate, Jesus confirmed the truth: "For this I was born and for this I came into the world, **to testify to the truth**. Everyone who belongs to the truth listens to my voice" [John 18:37]. Pilate asked: "What is truth?" [John 18:38]. Jesus did not answer! Did Pilate really not know? Was he "playing dumb" or did he want to avoid the truth? That is, in "The Word became flesh and dwelt among us. We have seen his glory, the glory of the only Son as of the Father, full of grace and truth" [John 1:14].

No one can obscure the truth, no one can distort the truth. However, throughout history as well as in life today, people still blatantly change the truth. How terrible! Saint Paul once exclaimed: "The mystery of iniquity is at work" [2 Thess 2:7]. And Saint Peter predicted: "The way of truth will be blasphemed" [2 Pet 2:2]. Regarding paying taxes to Caesar, they sent their disciples along with the Herodians to tell Jesus: "Teacher, we know that you are a truthful man and teach the way of God in accordance with the truth. You are not partial to anyone, for you do not judge people by their appearance" [Mt 22:16; Mc 12:14]. Even though they had only evil intentions and wanted to set a trap to harm Him, they themselves had to acknowledge the truth in Jesus.

Jesus is the truth, so He knows the truth of sin in every person. In addition to original sin, there is also personal sin. The story of the adulterer is recorded in the Gospel of John 7:53-8:11: Jesus went to the Mount of Olives. Early in the morning, He returned to the Temple. All the people came to Him. He sat down and taught them. At that time, the scribes and Pharisees brought before Jesus a woman who had been caught in adultery. They made her stand in the middle and said to Him, "Teacher, this woman was caught in the act of adultery. In the Law, Moses commanded us to stone such women. What do You think?" They said this to test Him, so that they could have evidence to accuse Him. But Jesus bent down and wrote with his finger on the ground. When they kept asking Him, He straightened up and said to them, "Let the one among you who is without sin be the first to throw a stone at her." Then he stooped down again and wrote on the ground. When they heard this, they went away one by one, beginning with the older ones. Jesus was left alone, with the woman standing in the middle. Jesus stood up and said to her, "Woman, where are they? Has no one condemned you?" She said to him, "No one, sir." Jesus said to her, "Neither do I condemn you. Go, and from now on do not sin again." Here Jesus wants to direct people to look into their own souls, so that they can recognize their own sins and recognize the truth within themselves. **So surely none of us is pure?** The answer is indeed like that.

Therefore, theologians define what happiness is and its origin: "O God, you are my God. Apart from you, there is no happiness" [Ps 16:2]. In God and in God, man knows that he will find complete happiness for life. That happiness is not just a fulfillment through temporary emotions, but the happiness of a loved one: "Live in intimacy with God and make peace, and you will find happiness" [Job 22:21].

In short, when discussing happiness from a philosophical or theological perspective, there is a common point that happiness is the truth. However, there is a difference between the two worldviews above: the source of truth from a philosophical perspective is from the very process of formation, existence and development of human beings; while for theologians, it is established by God. And that truth was distorted by the first human, through breaking the covenant with God. However, with love, God promised and blessed human beings with new happiness, but that happiness was not as complete as the original happiness (before our ancestors sinned).

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REFERENCES

- 1) Tran Phuc Nhan, Understanding the Old Testament c. Neal M. Flanagan, osm, Salvation History, Introduction to Biblical Theology.
- 2) J. Dheilly Desclee, Bible Dictionary – Part II (from DJ). Nguyen Dac Anh, Salvation History
- 3) Father Nguyen The Thuan , Bible – Translation. Publishing House , Press Department. 1976.
- 4) Neal M. Flanagan, Salvation History: Introduction to Biblical Theology.
- 5) Father Francois Viet. History of Salvation .
- 6) C.Marx and F.Engels: Complete Works, Vol.42, National Political Publishing House Truth, Hanoi, 2000.
- 7) C.Marx and F.Engels: Complete Works, Vol.20, National Political Publishing House Truth, Hanoi, 2002.
- 8) Minns, Denis, & Paul Parvis. Justin, Philosopher and Martyr: Apologies. Edited by Henry Chadwick, Oxford Early Christian Texts. Oxford: OUP, 2009.
- 9) Aurelius Augustine, The City of God, Book Thirteen - Reasoning. Reverend Marcus Dods, Ma.
- 10) Dinh Van Chien (2024) Moral thought in the wise speaker of qohelet king of jerusalem.
<https://www.ijsshmr.com/v3i11/Doc/9.pdf>
- 11) Dinh Van Chien (2024) Humanistic thought in jesus' sermon on the eight beatens.
https://www.pjlss.edu.pk/pdf_files/2024_2/15165-15170.pdf
- 12) Dinh Van Chien (2024) Moral thought in the wise speaker of qohelet king of Jerusalem
<https://www.ijsshmr.com/v3i11/Doc/9.pdf>
- 13) Wordnet 3.0 (accessed 2011-Feb-24 via Wolfram Alpha)
- 14) Borg, Marcus J. (2006). “The Spirit-Filled Experience of Jesus”. In Dunn, James DG; McKnight, Scott (editor). The Historical Jesus in Recent Research. p. 303. ISBN 1-57506-100-7 .
- 15) Green, Joel B.; McKnight, Scot; Marshall, I. Howard (1992). Dictionary of Jesus and the Gospels. InterVarsity Press. ISBN 9780830817771 .